

Ilorin Traditional Architecture as a Good Example of a Green Building Design

Authors : Olutola Funmilayo Adekeye

Abstract : Tradition African practice of architecture can be said to be deeply rooted in Green Architecture in concept, design and execution. A study into the ancient building techniques in Ilorin Emirate depicts prominent (eco-centric approach of) Green Architecture principles. In the Pre-colonial era before the introduction of modern architecture and Western building materials, the Nigeria traditional communities built their houses to meet their cultural, religious and social needs using mainly indigenous building materials such as mud (Amo), cowdung (Boto), straws (koriko), palm fronts (Imo-Ope) to mention a few. This research attempts to identify the various techniques of applying the traditional African principles of Green Architecture to Ilorin traditional buildings. It will examine and assess some case studies to understand the extent to which Green architecture principles have been applied to traditional building designs that are still preserved today in Ilorin, Nigeria. Furthermore, this study intends to answer many questions, which can be summarized into two basic questions which are: (1) What aspects of what today are recognized as important green architecture principles have been applied to Ilorin traditional buildings? (2) To what extent have the principles of green architecture applied to Ilorin traditional buildings been ways of demonstrating a cultural attachment to the earth as an expression of the African sense of human being as one with nature?

Keywords : green architecture, Ilorin, traditional buildings, design principles, ecocentric, application

Conference Title : ICBAU 2014 : International Conference on Building, Architecture and Urbanism

Conference Location : Toronto, Canada

Conference Dates : June 16-17, 2014